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Analysis of the performances of a solid oxide fuel cell fed by biogas in different plant configurations: An integrated experimental and simulative approach

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Low energy content biogas can be valorised in SOFCs, especially at small-scale
- Experimental results show good compatibility of SOFC & analyzed biogas matrices
- Simulation results are aligned with experimental data for outlet gas composition

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ABSTRACT

Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC) are efficient, modular and fuel-flexible high temperature electrochemical devices. SOFC systems can be coupled to biogas from anaerobic digestion plants to obtain efficient and decentralized CHP systems, maximizing the valorization of biogas in virtuous waste-to-energy schemes. The main challenges for biogas-SOFC plants are related to performance stability and degradation at process level. In this work the performance and stability of an electrolyte supported SOFC single cell (100 cm²) fed with biogas mixtures derived from different integrated biogas-SOFC CHP plant configurations (hot/cold recirculation; UF_f 65–85% - obtained from previous simulation work) has been analyzed with an integrated experimental and simulative approach. To support the experimental results, a chemical equilibrium model of the gas conversion processes coupled with the electrochemical conversion route is developed in MATLAB in order to simulate the gas composition at the anode outlet, which is compared and validated with experimental data obtained by Gas Chromatography (GC). Results show that suitable and stable cell performances are obtained while feeding the SOFC samples by biogas (720–800 mV; 0.16–0.2 W/cm² at 0.25 A/cm²) where the main performance losses are related to steam content - as well as other gas species, deriving from the pre-processing of the biogas. The gas composition and UF_f simulation results show good correspondence with the GC data (error range <5% for the matrix gases and <10% for water) highlighting that the SOFC

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processes under clean biogas can be successfully represented - to a certain extent - by a chemical equilibrium model.

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Nomenclature

Symbols

a	activity
A	Ampere
°C	Celsius degrees
cm	centimeters
F	Faraday constant
h	Hours
I	Current
kg	Kilograms
N	number of electrons
P	Pressure
T	Temperature
V	Voltage
W	Watt

Acronyms

AISI	American Iron and Steel Institute
CEM	Controlled Evaporator and Mixer
CGO	Gandolinium Doped Ceria
CHP	Cogeneration of Heat and Power
CRUFF85%	Cold Recirculation composition
ES-SOFC	Electrolyte Supported-SOFC
FC	Fuel Cell
GC	Gas Chromatography
HRUFF65%	Hot Recirculation composition
LSMC	Lanthanum Strontium Manganese Cobaltite
LSCF	Lanthanum Strontium Cobalt Ferrite
MCO	Manganese Cobalt Oxide
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
PID	Piping and Instrumentation Diagram
REFH2	Reference hydrogen composition
REV	Reversible
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
SMR	Steam Methane Reforming
TPB	Triple Phase Boundary
UF	Utilization Factor
WGS	Water Gas Shift

density and the great advantage of fuel flexibility, being able to process carbonaceous fuels thanks to the conversion reactions which occur within the cell [1,2]. Moreover, these devices have higher electrical efficiencies (60–70%) than traditional conversion systems (30–50%) due to direct energy conversion without thermodynamic cycle and can be used in CHP mode to recover high-grade heat [3]. In addition, since combustion is not present other pollutant emissions are avoided [4]. SOFCs can be competitive with traditional conversion systems especially for small plant sizes [5], because unlike conventional conversion systems or other combustion-driven technologies, they have excellent scalability. However, there are some constraints to the deployment of this technology, mainly related to investment cost and lifetime. Knowledge in terms of materials optimization [6], performance stability [7] and degradation mechanisms [8] are still a subject of research. Another issue, especially when powered with fuels other than H₂, is the role of contaminants and acceptable limit concentrations for proper operation [5].

Among the different fuels that can be used to power these devices, the operation of SOFCs coupled with bio-syngas produced by gasification or anaerobic digestion processes is a topic of great interest, due to the good compatibility between the two systems. Integrated biogas-SOFC systems would allow to maximize the production of clean energy from a low calorific value gas (between 4 and 7 kWh/Nm³ [9]) produced from biomass and/or waste, in virtuous waste-to-energy schemes [10–12], even at low/medium scales thanks to the excellent modularity and scalability of SOFCs. Valorization of waste biomass is also in line with the EU policy for clean energy production [13–15].

Different schemes of biogas-SOFC integration can be implemented such as direct feed of the dry CH₄/CO₂ mixture to the SOFC with dry conversion processes occurring internally to the cell itself [16–19] or via biogas pre-treatment, converting the biogas (typically in presence of steam) to a hydrogen rich syngas mixture (H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄, etc.) via chemical conversion reactors prior to the SOFC inlet [20,21]. However, integrated biogas-SOFC systems are complex as there are more chemical and electrochemical reactions to be considered. Different hurdles from a process point of view arise, related for example to the risk of carbon deposition in Ni-based electrodes with carbon-based fuels [22], sub-optimal thermal management due to endothermic reaction on the electrode layers [23,24] or possible degradation mechanisms related to contaminants (most critical ones in biogas are sulfur compounds, siloxanes and halogens) [3,20].

1. Introduction

Fuel Cells (FCs) are devices that allow to obtain direct chemical conversion of fuels into electricity. Among the different kind of FC, the Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs) have higher power

Many authors have analyzed different aspects of biogas-SOFC plants. Medium scale biogas-CHP (between 25 and 150 kW) has been studied in different conditions, such as coupled to a sewage sludge digestion plant with external steam reforming [25] or to an anaerobic digestion plant of municipal waste to supply energy for an energy community of around 50 households [26]. Hamdullahpur et al. [27] have evaluated the performance of different configurations of biogas-fueled SOFC micro-CHP systems for residential applications at few kW scale, as well as other authors [28]. Furthermore biogas-SOFC systems have also been studied even hybrid schemes with other systems such as micro gas turbines [29] as *m*-CHP and CHP plants. Although most studies evidence the potential and technical competitiveness of such solutions especially at small scales, also large scale (1 MW) centralized biogas-SOFC systems have been investigated [30]. Apart from theoretical studies, some biogas-SOFC demonstration plants have been realized at relevant scale (10–100 kW) as well [31–34], with parallel tests being carried out on laboratory and pilot-scale (1–10 kW) [35,36].

1.1. Techno-economic outlook of integrated biogas-SOFC systems

Integrated biogas-SOFC systems should also show suitable techno-economic characteristics in order to foster their competitiveness, with respect to conventional CHP technologies [37].

The most relevant technical parameters are related to the SOFC service life (current targets are 10,000–40,000 h of operation, with degradation rates of <1%/1000 h [8,38–42]), stability in presence of biogas contaminants (sulfur compounds, tars, siloxanes, halogens, VOC, etc. [5,43,44]) and cyclic stability (thermal cycling, electrical cycling, redox cycling, etc. [45–48]). However, considering that biogas-CHP systems typically operate as stationary co-generators (>7000 h/year, exploiting the batch reactor design of the digester which guarantees continuous production of biogas) the issues related to cyclability are mitigated since the SOFC unit is generally operating continuously close to its nominal operation point (net of start-up/shut-downs for maintenance periods, fluctuation of biogas flow and composition, etc.) [49].

From an economical point of view the main relevant parameter is related to the CAPEX of the anaerobic digester (between 1 and 5 k€/kW for small-scale digestors [50,51]) and SOFC systems (between 3 and 10 k€/kW_e [40,52–54]). For the SOFC systems, previously mentioned issues in service life and degradation indirectly causes high replacement costs, since the SOFC stack might require substitution after few years (40,000 h equal to 4–5 years of continuous operation).

In particular, integrated biogas-SOFC plants represent a promising CHP solution for small-size decentralized users (e.g. farms, wastewater treatment plants, municipal solid waste collection plants, etc.) operating on low-cost fuel produced from local waste resources [36,55,56]. As an example, the study by Majerus [51] shows how biogas-SOFC solutions are more competitive than ICE for a small-scale farm for SOFC and biogas digester costs below ca. 13 k€/kW and 2 k€/kW, respectively, which are rather attainable respect to the foreseen targets. Choosing a SOFC over an ICE allows to almost

double the net electricity production from biogas (due to increase of electrical efficiency), with target LCOE values of around 0.06–0.23 €/kWh [50,57–59]. In addition, the energy dependence of such users from grid infrastructures (both electricity and gas) could be reduced or even off-grid solutions (possibly also supported by local RES) could be evaluated. Optimization and tailoring of the relative sizes of the digester and SOFC stack will also play a key role in the determination of the economic competitiveness of integrated biogas-SOFC systems [60,61].

1.2. Objectives, scope and novelty of the study

Thus, the aim of this work is to evaluate the operation of an SOFC system fed with a biogas produced by anaerobic digestion process from different substrates to validate performance and stability under different conditions. Experimental tests with a laboratory-replica gas mixture have been carried out and a 0-D chemical model was also developed in MATLAB to calculate the composition of the anodic output and compare it with the results obtained from the tests. Although the used experimental and simulation methodologies are well-known, the novelty of this work concerns the link between the process and system level, in order to assess with an integrated approach different biogas-SOFC integration scenarios.

2. Materials & methods

This chapter discusses the procedures employed to study the behaviour of SOFCs during experimental campaigns and the theoretical relations used to develop a 0-dimensional equilibrium model in MATLAB to estimate fuel conversion, following both the chemical and electrochemical conversion routes.

The chapter is organized as follows: firstly a brief overview of the main involved SOFC processes when operated under a biogas feedstock is provided, secondarily the case study from the WASTE2WATTS project is presented in detail, thirdly the experimental campaigns are described and lastly the gas conversion model is presented.

2.1. SOFC process overview

SOFCs systems are fuel cell devices based on a solid-state electrolyte which is conductive for O²⁻ ions generated at the cathode by the reduction of O₂ present in the air, Equation (1). When it reaches the interface with the anode, at the triple phase boundary (TPB), it electro-oxidizes the fuel (typically hydrogen) releasing the electrons and generating water as a product, which is discharged at the outlet of the anode chamber - Equation (2). Direct CO and CH₄ electro-oxidation reactions (Equations (3) and (4)) are also possible but are typically disregarded due to slower reaction kinetics and high activation energy compared with H₂ electro-oxidation [20,62]. In fact, as an alternative to direct electro-oxidation, CH₄ and CO react chemically within the cell. If H₂O is present in the input composition, the two most probable reaction mechanisms are steam methane reforming (SMR), Equation (5), and Water Gas Shift (WGS), Equation (6). With these reactions, the

elements do not contribute directly to the electrochemical conversion but increase the amount of hydrogen in the mixture, which is subsequently oxidized. Some of the reactions that can take place inside the cell are listed below [3]:

From a thermodynamic point of view, the electrochemical performances of the SOFC cell are given by the operating conditions (temperature and pressure) and inlet/outlet streams compositions (as a result of the fuel conversion within the cell). The theoretical open circuit voltage (OCV) of the cell can be reasonably obtained from Nernst equation (Equation (7)) [63], where a is the activity of the different species. If the behaviour of the gasses can be assumed as ideal and the cell pressure is uniform and equal to the atmospheric pressure, the activities can be replaced with the partial pressures of the components.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Nernst voltage } E_{\text{rev}} &= E^0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln\left(\frac{a_{\text{products}}}{a_{\text{reagents}}}\right) \\ E_{\text{rev}} &= E^0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln\left(\frac{p_{\text{products}}}{p_{\text{reagents}}}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

2.2. W2W project case study definition

The present work aims to analyze two case studies of biogas-SOFC coupling in terms of fuel processing options within the WASTE2WATTS (W2W) EU project [64]. Analyzing the availability of biomass resources in different EU countries, representative biogas matrices were chosen as output of the anaerobic digestion processes of target feedstocks (agricultural manure biomass, organic fraction of municipal solid waste, landfill biomass). Excluding landfill biomass due to higher dilution in N₂ (up to 10–20%_{v,oi}) and higher content of contaminants (siloxanes, halogens and VOC) [65], the focus was put on agricultural sources and organic fraction of municipal solid waste which share a typical raw biogas CH₄/CO₂ composition of around 60/40%_{v,oi} and lower content of contaminants [66–68]. The raw biogas at the output of the digester is sent to a sorbent-based cleaning reactor whose main role is to abate sulfur compounds (both organic and inorganic) up to tolerable limits for the SOFC (ppm level) [69], as well as remove other harmful contaminants (siloxanes, halogens, VOC, NH₃, etc.). In addition, in-digester sulfur abatement solutions can also be implemented (e.g.

introduction of FeCl₂ catalyst, addition of air, etc.) to reduce the contaminant levels [70]. Subsequently, the gas is sent to the SOFC unit with different fuel processing options (biogas reforming and conditioning – with a pre-reformer reactor

based on Ni and Ru catalyst optimized for steam and dry reforming respectively [71]) and plant configurations of the SOFC modules (anode off-gas recirculation and thermal management strategy) are analyzed in the project to assess the performance of an integrated biogas-SOFC CHP systems with minimal gas conditioning and thermal system integration as downstream technology in anaerobic digestion processes [72].

In particular, the two cases analyzed in this study are: 1) Hot Recirculation (HR), where the anode off-gas is recirculated back to the inlet of the SOFC pre-reformer, modifying the gas conditioning step of the biogas; 2) Cold Recirculation (CR), where part of the anode off-gas is sent to an after burner to cover internal heat loads and part of the off-gas is sent to a water knock-out reactor and then recirculated to the inlet of the SOFC pre-reformer. Thus in the HR configuration the recirculated gas is mainly composed of residual fuel and product H₂O, while in the CR case the recirculated gas is mainly composed of CO₂. The specific gas operating conditions (gas compositions and fuel utilization factors UF_f) of the two cases were obtained by previous simulation work of the two plant layouts with Aspen Plus [72].

Fig. 1 represents the different integrated biogas-SOFC plant configurations analyzed in this paper (which are only part of those analyzed in the W2W project).

2.3. Description of the experimental campaigns

Cell and Housing. An electrolyte-supported solid oxide fuel cell (ES-SOFC) manufactured from Sunfire which are composed of state-of-the-art materials (reported in Table 1) was tested. Cell samples with 10 × 10 cm (100 cm²) square configuration, with a resulting active area of 9 × 9 cm (81 cm²) have been used for the experimental analysis. The main characteristics of the cell samples can be found in [73]. In Fig. 2 cell configurations are shown together with SEM images of the anode in which the different components and layers can be distinguished.

Fig. 1 – Integrated biogas-SOFC plant layouts from the W2W project, adapted from Ref. [72].

The cell is mounted in the housing and set up in the furnace as shown in Fig. 3. The cell housing consists in: inlet and outlet pipes (Inconel); anode and cathode cases in which the cell is housed (AISI 310S); gas distribution plates (AISI 310S) coated with manganese oxide (MCO); current collectors (nickel mesh on the anode side and gold mesh grid on the cathode side); gas sealing gaskets (Thermiculite).

Test rig. After the assembly, the cell is placed in a custom temperature-controlled furnace heated by electric resistors. The supply of the different gas species is provided by a set of Mass Flow Controllers (Bronkhorst – EL Flow). Steam – which is necessary to support the WGS and SMR reactions and to avoid carbon deposition – is added in the anode gas flow via a Controlled Evaporator and Mixer (Bronkhorst – CEM) supplied by demineralized water. After the CEM, the piping is equipped with trace heaters (Watlow) to prevent condensation. The connection to the electrical load is done through the metallic cell holder itself and the voltage is measured with Pt wires in contact with the current collectors. Separate wires are used for current loading and voltage sensing to avoid affecting the measured value. Finally, Gas Chromatography (PerkinElmer – Clarus 680) measurements are carried out from gas samples taken at the anode outlet. Fig. 4 shows a conceptual scheme of the test rig.

Test procedures. The procedures followed to reach operating conditions are: (1) heating from room temperature to 850 °C at a rate of 1 °C/min with inert gas (N₂) at the anode and air at the cathode; (2) reduction of the NiO to metallic Ni in the anode by inserting a progressively increasing flow of hydrogen from 5% to 50% of the total gas mixture for around 1 h; (3) cell stabilization by operation with a reference test (namely REFH2:

H₂/N₂ 60/40%_{v,vol}; 486 Nml/min; the specific flow rate is equal to 6 Nml/min.cm² as defined by the cell manufacturer and other testing partners in the project, scaled to the tested cell geometry) for around 50–200 h (Table 2); (4) operation with biogas mixtures for around 250 h (Table 2).

As previously described, the two different case studies are related to the HR and CR plant layout scenarios and the numerical values of the operating conditions (flow rates, compositions and UF_f) are derived from previous simulative work [72]. The selected compositions, flow rates and UF_f are the result of a system-level optimization process which aims to maximize the plant efficiency by varying the external reformer temperature and anode off-gas recirculation rate, while at the same time minimize or completely avoid the external supply of steam to the fuel conditioning step (external reformer) to avoid carbon deposition (thermodynamic equilibrium calculations, which can be translated on the C–H–O ternary diagram [74]). The anode flow rates and compositions used are summarised in Table 2.

Among the various scenarios obtained from the results of the system-level simulation, a UF_f of 65% has been selected for the HR case (namely HRUFF65%) since the fuel is richer in fuel content, while for the CR case – characterized by lower fuel content – the UF_f is increased to 85% (namely CRUFF85%) to obtain a suitable power output.

The SOFC cells are characterized by means of: 1) polarization curves (I, V), by step-wise current sweep up to slightly higher than the nominal current (20 A, with steps of 1 A); 2) voltage stability curves (t, V), in galvanostatic conditions at the nominal current (19 A); 3) Gas Chromatography (GC) measurements of samples of the anode output.

Several long-term stability tests (between 100 and 500 h) under a fixed load current of 19 A (0.235 A/cm²) were carried out with different phases, as reported in Table 3. The temperature level of 850 °C is fixed from the design operating temperature of the ES-SOFC. Dead weight between 10 and 30 kg is applied on top of the cell to improve the electrical contact, if needed. The different test phases lasted several hours (between 50 and 250 h) during which the operating voltage was measured continuously, the measurements related to polarization curves and Gas Chromatography were carried out at a periodicity of approximately 50 h/test. Due to time constraints, the HRUFF65% condition was tested in two identical samples (Test 1 and Test 2), while the CRUFF85% was tested for only one sample.

From the GC measurement, the experimental UF_f is calculated by considering the variation of fuel elements (CH₄, CO, H₂ in hydrogen equivalent – see next section Model Description) between the inlet and outlet compositions. Since the test bench setup does not present a direct measurement of the outlet gas flow rate, this value was preliminarily assumed equal to the inlet flow rate, net of the volume increase of the SMR reaction. However, possible leakages in the test bench could lead to a reduction of the actual value of the anode outlet flow rate. This could lead to underestimation of the experimental UF_f respect to the nominal value expected with the imposed current. Thus, a manual correction of the anode

Table 1 – Materials and thickness of the cell components [73].

Component	Material	Thickness (μm)
Anode	Ni-CGO	25
Electrolyte	YSZ	80–85
Cathode	LSCF-CGO	30–35

Fig. 2 – Cell representation and SEM images of Anode layer, adapted from Ref. [73].

Fig. 3 – Assembly procedure, single cell, housing and test station.

outlet flow rate can be introduced to realign the UF_f back to the nominal expected one.

Since the study is carried out at single cell level, the experimental campaign is mainly focused on performance and stability of the SOFC samples under the different biogas integration scenarios rather than on conversion efficiency (since the single cell is not representative of the system level) and degradation (longer exposure times would be required to extrapolate relevant degradation rates).

2.4. Model Description

In order to calculate the composition of the anode gas exiting the cells used in the tests a simple chemical model at thermodynamic equilibrium was developed in MATLAB based on a previous code structure developed in the same group [23].

For sake of simplicity, the process was conceptually divided into two phases, first a chemical conversion of CH_4

ENEAS SINGLE CELL TEST BENCH

Fig. 4 – Conceptual scheme of the experimental test bench facility.

Table 2 – Analysed experimental testing conditions.

Reference conditions (REFH2)			
REFH2 (1)	Flow rate (ml/min)	Molar flow (mol/min)	Composition (%)
H ₂	292	1.30E-02	60%
N ₂	194	8.65E-03	40%
Total	486	2.17E-02	100%
Hot Recirculation conditions; nominal Utilization Factor fuel 65% (HRUFF65%)			
HRUFF65%	Flow rate (ml/min)	Molar flow (mol/min)	Composition (%)
H ₂	114	5.09E-03	36%
CO	82	3.66E-03	26%
CO ₂	57	2.54E-03	18%
H ₂ O	54	2.41E-03	17%
CH ₄	3	1.34E-04	1%
N ₂	6	2.68E-04	2%
Total	316	1.41E-02	100%
Cold Recirculation conditions; nominal Utilization Factor fuel 85% (CRUFF85)			
CRUFF85%	Flow rate (ml/min)	Molar flow (mol/min)	Composition (%)
H ₂	35	1.56E-03	5%
CO	124	5.53E-03	18%
CO ₂	434	1.94E-02	63%
H ₂ O	76	3.39E-03	11%
CH ₄	0	0.00 E+00	0%
N ₂	20	8.92E-04	3%
Total	689	3.07E-02	100%

Table 3 – Summary of the tests carried out.

Test parameter	HRUFF65% (1)	HRUFF65% (2)	CRUFF85%
Temperature (°C)	850	850	850
Pressure (bar)	1	1	1
Current density (A/cm ²)	0.235	0.235	0.235
Applied weight (kg)	10	30	10
Hydrogen stabilization (h)	260	70	145
Biogas feed (h)	240	47	267
Total (h)	500	117	412

and CO into H₂ via SMR and WGS reactions (Equations (5) and (6)). Subsequently, the total hydrogen (sum of the hydrogen provided as input and produced by the chemical reactions) reacts by electro-oxidation reaction (Equation (2)).

The input conditions are determined by the testing parameters (cell temperature T and pressure p, current density) and fuel inlet conditions (biogas composition), as well as the cell design parameters (active surface area, etc.).

The operation represented by the model has been developed under several assumptions: (1) system at chemical equilibrium at the cell operating temperature T; (2) uniform anodic and cathodic fluxes in time; (3) CO and CH₄ contribute to the conversion process only through the WGS and SMR; (4) sequence of reactions is SMR → WGS → H₂ electro-oxidation; (5) T and p uniform and constant with time (atmospheric pressure is considered); (6) all gases are assumed as ideal.

By the stoichiometry of the reactions considered in the model (Equations (8)–(13)) the concentrations leaving the system were expressed as a function of the input concentrations and the reacted quantities x, y and z within the cell, which are therefore the unknown variables of the problem:

$$\text{CH}_4^{\text{out}} = \text{CH}_4^{\text{in}} - x \quad (8)$$

$$\text{CO}^{\text{out}} = \text{CO}^{\text{in}} + x - y \quad (9)$$

$$\text{CO}_2^{\text{out}} = \text{CO}_2^{\text{in}} + y \quad (10)$$

$$\text{H}_2^{\text{out}} = \text{H}_2^{\text{in}} + x + y - z \quad (11)$$

$$\text{H}_2\text{O}^{\text{out}} = \text{H}_2\text{O}^{\text{in}} - x - y + z \quad (12)$$

$$Q_{\text{anode tot}}^{\text{out}} = Q_{\text{anode tot}}^{\text{in}} + 2x \quad (13)$$

It is worth emphasizing that due to the steam reforming reaction not being equimolar, the total output volumetric flow rate is increased compared to the input flow rate by a factor of 2x.

From the assumption that the only chemical element that performs an electro-oxidation is H₂ it is possible to derive z from the relationship that links the electron flow generated by the electro-oxidation of H₂ to the current:

$$z = I/2F \quad (14)$$

In order to obtain the relations to derive x and y, assuming that SMR and WGS reach the equilibrium at the cell operating temperature, it is possible to express the ratio between the

partial pressures of products and reactants as a function of the equilibrium constants of the two analyzed reactions, which is in turn defined at the cell operating temperature. In addition, under atmospheric and uniform pressure the partial pressures can be replaced by the volume fractions (Equations (15) and (16)).

$$K_{eq_SMR}(T) + \frac{\left(\frac{H_2^{out}}{Q_{an_tot}^{out}}\right)^3 \left(\frac{CO^{out}}{Q_{an_tot}^{out}}\right)}{\left(\frac{CH_4^{out}}{Q_{an_tot}^{out}}\right) \left(\frac{H_2O^{out}}{Q_{an_tot}^{out}}\right)} \quad (15)$$

$$K_{eq_WGS}(T) + \frac{\left(\frac{H_2^{out}}{Q_{an_tot}^{out}}\right) \left(\frac{CO^{out}}{Q_{an_tot}^{out}}\right)}{\left(\frac{CO^{out}}{Q_{an_tot}^{out}}\right) \left(\frac{H_2O^{out}}{Q_{an_tot}^{out}}\right)} \quad (16)$$

The values of the equilibrium constants K_{eq} for both reactions were derived as a function of temperature by means of an empirical polynomial formulation (Equation (17)) where the values of the constants were taken from the literature values reported in Massardo and Lubelli [75] and Chen et al. [76] and their values are given in Table 4.

$$\log(K_{eq}) = AT^4 + BT^3 + CT^2 + DT + E \quad (17)$$

Thus, all quantities in the functions are known except for x and y . The system studied is therefore composed of two non-linear equations (Equations (18) and (19)) in two unknowns.

$$f_1 = -K_{eq_SMR} + \frac{\left(\frac{H_2^{in} + 3x + y - z}{Q_{an_tot}^{in} + 2x}\right)^3 \left(\frac{CO^{in} + x - y}{Q_{an_tot}^{in} + 2x}\right)}{\left(\frac{CH_4^{in} - x}{Q_{an_tot}^{in} + 2x}\right) \left(\frac{H_2O^{in} - x - y + z}{Q_{an_tot}^{in} + 2x}\right)} \quad (18)$$

$$f_2 = -K_{eq_WGS} + \frac{\left(\frac{H_2^{in} + 3x + y - z}{Q_{an_tot}^{in} + 2x}\right) \left(\frac{CO^{in} + y}{Q_{an_tot}^{in} + 2x}\right)}{\left(\frac{CO^{in} + x - y}{Q_{an_tot}^{in} + 2x}\right) \left(\frac{H_2O^{in} - x - y + z}{Q_{an_tot}^{in} + 2x}\right)} \quad (19)$$

In order to obtain a solution for the two variables, a MATLAB script based on the *fsolve* function was implemented. The script identifies the roots of the two functions, representing the solutions for x and y , by means of a trust region-Dogleg algorithm, starting from a first attempt solution inserted as input.

After calculating the output quantities, it was finally possible to calculate the fuel Utilization Factor (UF_f) with a bottom-up approach based on the difference between inlet/outlet equivalent hydrogen concentration ($H_{2\ out/in}$ to which the quantities produced by CH_4 and CO must then be added) contained in the fuel elements in the mixture.

$$UF = 1 - \frac{(4CH_{4\ OUT} + CO_{OUT} + H_{2\ OUT}) \cdot Q_{TOT\ AN\ OUT}}{(4CH_{4\ IN} + CO_{IN} + H_{2\ IN}) \cdot Q_{TOT\ AN\ IN}} \quad (20)$$

Finally, the results in terms of flow rate and gas composition at the outlet of the anode chamber and the utilization factor obtained from the model were compared with the experimental values obtained through Gas Chromatography. An analysis of the error and error bands of the experimental measurements was also carried out.

3. Results & discussion

3.1. Experimental results

In this section the main results in terms of electrochemical performances and gas conversion are reported for the different plant configurations and nominal testing conditions.

HRUFF65% test results. In the first two experiments the SOFC cells are tested under a biogas composition representing a hot recirculation of the anode output with an UF_f equal to 65%, namely HRUFF65% (see Fig. 5).

Given the conditions used in the two tests are the same, the results show the same overall trend in the cell performances for both REFH2 and HRUFF65% conditions, net of slight differences attributable to the setup and assembly. In the second test it was necessary to increase the weight from 10 kg to 30 kg to improve contact with the current collector (as seen in the first 60 h of operation in REFH2).

Overall, the performance and stability (net of some voltage oscillation noise caused by water vapour presence) are acceptable in both tests. The voltage performance obtained in REFH2 is in line with the ranges indicated by the cell manufacturer, and when supplied with HRUFF65%, the obtained values match the ones calculated by previous modelling work [72]. Table 5 summarizes voltage and power outputs obtained in OCV and operating conditions.

The differences between operation with pure hydrogen and biogas are greatest at OCV (mainly due to the difference in gas composition) and decrease as the current density increases. The explanation for this phenomenon is associated with the presence of H_2O in the biogas mixture, which lowers the open-circuit voltage value following the Nernst equation [63], and facilitates the diffusion of H_2 to the TPB by lowering polarization losses [22,23].

From the GC analysis, CH_4 is not recorded at the output. As CH_4 is only at 3% at the input, it is reasonable to assume that it is completely converted through SMR. The percentage of CO goes from 26% input to 13.4% and 12.2% thus is consumed for about 50%. H_2 is present at the input at 36% and after being enriched by SMR and WGS reactions and consumed by electro-oxidation, is recorded at the output at 12.6% and 16.7%. The H_2O recorded at the output is only slightly lower than that at the input as water is both consumed within the cell by the SMR and WGS reactions and produced by the electro-oxidation of H_2 .

Mean experimental UF_f values calculated with Equation (20) - equal to 55–60% - are slightly lower than those expected by approximately 10%. The reason for such deviation is

Table 4 – Constants used in the empirical formulation to derive equilibrium constants.

	SMR	WGS
A	–2.6312E-11	5.4700E-12
B	1.2406E-07	–2.5740E-08
C	–2.2523E-04	4.6374E-05
D	1.9503E-01	–3.9150E-02
E	–6.6139 E+01	1.3210 E+01

Fig. 5 – (I,V), (t, V) and GC measurements for HRUFF65% tests. On the top Test 1 results, on the bottom Test 2 results.

Table 5 – Voltage and Power outputs in OCV and operating conditions for HRUFF65%.

	I (A/cm ²)	V (mV)	Power (W/cm ²)
REFH2 test 1	0	1092	0
	0.235	840	0.197
HRUFF65% test 1	0	957	0
	0.235	797	0.187
REFH2 test 2	0	1050	0
	0.235	810	0.190
HRUFF65% test 2	0	945	0
	0.235	776	0.182

possibly linked to a variation of the total anode outlet flow rate which is not accounted for in the GC measurements. In fact, decreasing the value of the output flow rate by approximately 10–20% yields to UF_f values comparable to those expected.

CRUFF85% test results. In the third experiment the SOFC sample is tested under a composition representing a biogas

matrix resulting from a cold recirculation plant configuration with an UF_f equal to 85%, namely CRUFF85% (see Fig. 6).

Also in this case, the operation of the cell in REFH2 is stable and in line with the values reported by the manufacturer, confirming that the cell is operating correctly. In CRUFF85% conditions, the performance is considerably lower than the one measured with the HRUFF65%, mainly because the gas composition has only 23% of combustible elements, represented by 5% hydrogen and 18% carbon monoxide. However, even with such a fuel lean gas, the cell is still able to deliver 715 mV and 0.16 W/cm², with a rather stable output profile which can be nevertheless satisfactory for certain applications (see Table 6).

From Gas Chromatography measurements, CO is reduced from 18% to values between 5% and 7%. CO reduction can be related to the evolution of the WGS reaction since also the CO₂ is increased from 63% to 71–75%. H₂, despite the increase caused by the WGS reaction of CO, is – from an overall point of view – reduced from 5% to 1% due to the electro-oxidation highlighting the high value of UF_f in this configuration. The trends in composition are more difficult to observe due to a

Fig. 6 – (I,V), (t, V) and GC measurements for CRUFF85% test.

Table 6 – Voltage and Power outputs in OCV and operating conditions for CRUFF65%.

	I (A/cm ²)	V (mV)	Power (W/cm ²)
REFH2 test 3	0	1131	0.000
	0.235	862	0.203
CRUFF85% test 3	0	880	0.000
	0.235	715	0.168

high presence of CO₂, which does not allow an easy reading of the results of the other gas species.

The mean experimental UF_f value calculated with Equation (20) is equal to 64.16%, considerably lower than the 85% expected with this composition. This could be linked higher leakage rates since the nominal inlet flow rate of the CR case is twice the one of the HR cases (689 ml/min vs. 316 ml/min, respectively). In addition, since there are very few combustible elements in the mixture, small variations of the anode outlet composition can lead to significative variations of the calculated experimental UF_f . A correction of the value of the output flow rate by approximately 50% yields to UF_f values comparable to those expected.

Overall test comparison. In Fig. 7 the overall comparison between all the tested samples is given (both under REFH2 and biogas feed). Under REFH2 conditions the cell performances are all quite similar (within the $\pm 5\%$ range, validating the testing setup [77,78]). Under biogas feed the performances in the CRUFF85% case are sensibly lower respect to the

HRUFF65%. This is explained with the lower content of fuel in the mixture, in alignment with the plant configuration.

3.2. Model results

In this section, the results of the gas conversion model are presented for the different plant configurations and nominal testing conditions.

HRUFF65% simulation results. The main results obtained from the model for the HRUFF65% case are reported in Table 7, variations between inlet and outlet compositions in the chemical-electrochemical steps have been shown also graphically in Fig. 8 for an easier reading of the results. In the intermediate step of chemical conversion, the effects of the SMR and WGS reactions are observed: CH₄ and CO at the input react with the H₂O consuming it almost completely to produce H₂ and CO₂. The CH₄ being present at only 3% is completely reformed, more than half of the CO (from 26% as input to 11% in the intermediate chemical conversion phase) is consumed by WGS. In equilibrium conditions the WGS reaction does not consume all the available CO. In the transition from chemical to electrochemical output, the only changes are due to the conversion of H₂ into H₂O, both due to the hydrogen electro-oxidation reaction considered in the model. The calculated UF_f (equal to 63.67%) is in line with the nominal value for the HRUFF65% composition (Table 8).

CRUFF85% simulation results. Similarly, the main results obtained from the model for the CRUFF85% case are reported in Table 9. Each gas conversion step has also been shown

Fig. 7 – Overall comparison between all the test. On the left REFH2 on the right biogas.**Table 7 – Model output for Hot Recirculation case.**

	Input (ml/min)		Chemical conversion (ml/min)		Output chemical conversion (ml/min)		Electro-chemical conversion (ml/min)		Output (ml/min)
CH ₄	3	-x	-2.9997		0.0003				0.0003
H ₂	114	3x + y	58.9622		172.9622	-z	-132.4394		40.5228
CO	82	x-y	-46.9634		35.0366				35.0366
CO ₂	57	y	49.9631		106.9631				106.9631
H ₂ O	54	-x-y	-52.9628		1.0372	z	132.4394		133.4766
N ₂	6	\	0		6				6
Tot	316	2x	5.9994		321.9994				321.9994

Fig. 8 – Model output for Hot Recirculation case.

Table 8 – Model calculation of UF_f for HR case.

Model Utilization Factor fuel UF_f		
Fuel in	208.00	ml/min
Fuel out	75.56	ml/min
Fuel reacted	132.44	ml/min
UF_f	63.67%	

Table 10 – Model calculation of UF_f for CR case.

Model Utilization Factor fuel UF_f		
Fuel in	159.00	ml/min
Fuel out	26.32	ml/min
Fuel reacted	132.68	ml/min
UF_f	83.45%	

graphically in Fig. 9 for an easier reading of the results. Already from the inlet, it is possible to observe the lack of fuel elements in this composition and the predominant presence of CO_2 . In the intermediate phase of chemical conversion, H_2O assumes a negative value that becomes positive again after electro-chemical conversion. This means that the WGS reaction in the chemical conversion step would require more water than what is provided in the inlet composition to reach equilibrium. However, the WGS should not be limited since additional H_2O can be supplied as produced of the electro-oxidation of hydrogen (the presence of negative values of H_2O is related to the fact that the model assumes SMR, WGS and H_2 electro-oxidation reactions to occur sequentially, while in reality these are simultaneous), provided that the final results of the volumetric flow rates for all gas species are ≥ 0 (Equation (21)).

$$H_2O^{out} = H_2O^{in} + z - x - y \geq 0 \quad (21)$$

Not being present in the input composition the CH_4 is equal to 0 and the SMR reaction does not occur, while the progress of the CO water gas shift reaction is 83.7%. The calculated utilization factor (83.5%) is aligned with the nominal value for the CRUFF85% composition (Table 10).

3.3. Comparison between experimental and model results

Although a highly simplified thermodynamic model has been utilized, good correspondence was found between calculated and experimental values. Errors respect to the experimental values are all within the 5% range with the exception of H_2O in the second test with HRUFF65%. However, this was expectable

Table 9 – Model output for Cold Recirculation case.

	Input (ml/min)	Chemical conversion (ml/min)	Output chemical conversion (ml/min)	Electro-chemical conversion (ml/min)	Output (ml/min)
CH_4	0	-x	0	0	0
H_2	35	$3x + y$	103.8019	138.8019	6.1186
CO	124	$x - y$	-103.8019	20.1981	20.1981
CO_2	434	y	103.8019	537.8019	537.8019
H_2O	76	$-x - y$	-103.8019	-27.8019	104.8814
N_2	20	\	0	20	20
Tot	689	$2x$	0	689	689

Fig. 9 – Model output for Cold Recirculation case.

since the GC instrument cannot directly measure H₂O concentration, hence H₂O content is calculated by difference with respect to the other gas species and it can be affected by a larger measurement error.

HRUFF65% - comparison of results. The gas composition results (%) of the model are compared with the experimental values obtained from GC measurements in Fig. 10 and Table 11. Overall, the trend for all elements is respected. Specifically, the CO output of the model seems to be underestimated, indicating that the equilibrium model overestimates the progress of the WGS reaction compared to what is observed in the experimental results. The main source of error is the estimation of the H₂O, for which the experimental setup presents some limitations since the H₂O is calculated by difference from the GC.

The experimental UF_f values are lower than those calculated by the model (which is in line with the nominal value of 65%) by approximately 10% (see Fig. 11). The reason for such deviation is possibly linked to a variation of the total anode outlet flow rate which is not accounted for in the GC measurements. The expected values for UF_f can be obtained based on the GC results by correcting the value of the outlet flow rate to by around 10–20% of the input flow rate.

3.3.1. CRUFF85% - comparison of results

Similarly, the gas composition results (%) of the model are compared with the experimental values in Fig. 12 and Table 12. Also with this gas matrix there is a good correspondence between the composition values calculated by the model and those obtained with the experimental results, with a

Fig. 10 – Comparison between model and experimental results for HR cases.

Table 11 – Comparison between model and experimental results for HR cases.

	Model Output	GC mean output		Error (x _{exp} -x _{model})	
		HRUFF65% Test 1	HRUFF65% Test 2	HRUFF65% Test 1	HRUFF65% Test 2
CH ₄	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
H ₂	13.11%	12.65%	16.66%	0.46%	3.55%
CO	10.14%	13.37%	12.21%	3.23%	2.07%
CO ₂	32.63%	32.69%	34.08%	0.06%	1.45%
H ₂ O	42.28%	38.03%	34.76%	4.25%	7.52%
N ₂	1.85%	3.24%	2.31%	1.39%	0.46%
				Mean error	
				1.57%	2.51%

UF _f comparison	
UF _f nominal	65%
UF _f model	63.67%
UF _f exp	55-60%

Fig. 11 – Comparison between model and experimental output of UF_f for HR composition.

Fig. 12 – Comparison between model and experimental results for CR case.

Table 12 – Comparison between model and experimental results for CR case.

	Model Output	CRUFF85%	Error ($x_{exp}-x_{model}$)
CH ₄	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
H ₂	0.89%	1.27%	0.38%
CO	2.93%	6.81%	3.88%
CO ₂	78.06%	73.67%	4.39%
H ₂ O	15.22%	14.75%	0.47%
N ₂	2.90%	3.48%	0.58%
			Mean error
			1.62%

maximum error of 4.38% and a mean error of only 1.61% for all elements. The greatest deviation is with CO and CO₂, supporting the hypothesis that the WGS reaction evolution is overestimated respect to the experimental values.

As shown in Fig. 13, also in this case the value of the UF_f obtained with the model (83.5%) is in line with the nominal value (85%). However, the mean experimental value is much lower (65%). The reasons for this difference could be the same as those already mentioned. The expected values for UF_f can

UF_f Comparison	
UF_f nominal	85%
UF_f model	83.45%
UF_f exp	64.16%

be obtained based on the GC results by correcting the value of the outlet flow rate to be around 50% of the input flow rate.

4. Conclusions

Overall, the two different biogas-SOFC scenarios have been analyzed in detail with a experimental and simulative approach, showing the competitiveness of SOFC systems as co-generators coupled with biogas resources. The loss of performances due to the biogas feeding are largely compensated by the opportunity of high efficiency CHP solutions using a fuel which can be produced locally and sustainably from waste, as a suitable alternative to the production and distribution of pure H₂ or other energy vectors, especially at small scale.

The SOFC performances results under the analyzed mixtures (derived from the different integrated biogas-SOFC plant configurations) are acceptable and show good stability, demonstrating good compatibility of SOFCs with biogas feedstocks. The performances obtained with the hot recirculation HRUFF65% case (775–800 mV and 0.180–0.190 W/cm² at around 0.25 A/cm²) are better than those obtained in the cold

Fig. 13 – Comparison between model and experimental output of UF_f for CR composition.

recirculation CRUFF85% case (715 mV and 0.170 W/cm² at around 0.25 A/cm²), mainly due to the lower content of fuel elements in the biogas mixture. However, CR cases could be an interesting scenario in terms of valorization of a lower added value fuel, with a higher overall energy utilization at plant & system level.

From a modelling perspective the SMR reaction is strongly favored by the high operating temperature (and Ni catalyst) completely converting all the CH₄ present in the inlet. Instead, the WGS reaction at equilibrium does not completely convert all the CO present in the mixture (already present in the inlet and produced by SMR). Kinetic behaviour of WGS reaction occurring internally to the SOFC itself may represent a limiting factor in the utilization of a simplified chemical equilibrium model for gas conversion. The simulation results highlight the importance of H₂O content since it is both consumed (by SMR and WGS) and produced (by electro-oxidation of H₂). H₂O content should be carefully addressed to meet the conversion requirements of SOFC systems fed by biogas, impacting the fuel pre-processing steps.

The simulation results show good alignment with the experimental values in terms of outlet anode gas composition with an error range <5% for the matrix gases (H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄) and <10% for H₂O. The higher error could be related to the greater measurement error in the GC, since the H₂O content is calculated by difference respect to the other gas species. The simulation results in terms of UF_f are also quite aligned to the nominal ones expected for the test, while the values calculated from the GC outlet data lead to lower values, which could be due to possible leakages in the test bench which affect the flow rate of the anode outlet gas. Since the CR is characterized by lower content of fuel elements, a small difference in the flow rate or gas composition leads to a higher impact in the UF_f. This allows to conclude that – to a certain extent – the SOFC processes can be in first approximation resembled by simple chemical equilibrium models which can provide a rough estimation of the evolution of the main chemical conversion reactions, mainly SMR and WGS.

The main perspectives for future work in this field are related to detailed impedance-based analyses with clean biogas and/or in presence of contaminants and system integration analysis to optimize the plant efficiency for the different gas processing options.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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